

Public Debt Management in Nepal: Current Position and Future Consequences

 Baburam Bhul

Executive Summary

The purpose of this article is to analyze the present status of public debt management in Nepal and its growing challenges and consequences. Public debt management has been well-known in recent years, and it is now widely acknowledged that, despite its tight ties to monetary and fiscal policy, debt management has its own distinct goals and tools. Public debt management is the process of creating and carrying out a plan to manage the government's debt in order to secure the required money over the medium to long term at the least expensive price possible, consistent with a prudent level of risk. This article is based on the descriptive research design based on the scoping review of secondary data and information used for the analysis and interpretation of the information. Public debt is the instrument for financing a budget deficit. One important macroeconomic problem of the Nepalese economy is the prevailing resource gap. Due to such situations, with the increase in the size of the government budget, the size of public debt is also increasing. With the increase in public debt, it is worthwhile to study how macroeconomic indicators are changing over time. According to recent data from the Public Debt Management Office (PDMO), the total government debt reached NPR 2007.84 billion at the end of the

 PhD Scholar in Management, Nepal Open University (NOU). Section Officer, Office of the Auditor General, Kathmandu, Nepal

1st quarter of FY 2079/80 (Oct 2022). Out of this amount, external debt is NPR 1050.23 billion and internal debt is NPR 957.61 billion. During this time, the total debt to GDP ratio reached 21.64 percent and the internal debt to GDP ratio reached 19.73 percent. Public debt raised at 41.5 percent of GDP at the end of FY 2021/22 and is split approximately evenly between external and domestic sources. Thus, the Nepalese economy is facing the problem of a low rate of economic growth and a high rate of inflation. However, economic governance is not enough to avoid the negative debt effect. Trade balance seems to be a more crucial factor than institutional quality on which the threshold level depends.

Keywords: public debt, fiscal deficit, debt trap, GDP, pandemic, PDMO, Nepal

Background

Over the last decade, there has been widespread agreement that good public debt management (PDM) can assist governments in lowering borrowing costs, containing financial risk, and developing their domestic debt market. It can also aid in the maintenance of financial stability and the development of their domestic financial system. While this is true for all countries, the needs and limits that countries face while creating good PDM systems vary depending on factors such as each country's level of development. Thus, while developed-country knowledge and techniques are obviously beneficial, emerging markets and low-income nations require solutions adapted to their specific demands and constraints: a "cookie cutter" approach would not suffice. Furthermore, debt management strategies must be integrated into an entire macroeconomic policy framework that promotes stability and growth. The finest debt management, in particular, cannot compensate for fiscal policies that result in unsustainable debt or irregular financing demands. A monetary policy that keeps inflation low will also make it easier to issue debt in home currency. The cost of borrowing can be decreased in many different ways with effective public debt management. Investor trust can be increased and the lending spread decreased by a carefully thought out and executed borrowing programme (Baliño and Sundararajan, 2008). Being able to invest in public debt securities that serve as standards for the price of other products and are readily available to domestic financial institutions is advantageous. Additionally, businesses and people both profit for related factors. A strong domestic financial sector can also help the economy grow and strengthen its resistance to foreign shocks like capital flight.

Growing public debt is a worldwide phenomenon that has become a common feature of the financial sectors of most economies. Current economic wisdom does not consider public debt a major problem rather the problem is the mismanagement and unsustainability of the public debt. Establishing debt management objectives, understanding the costs and risks associated with various strategies, and having a strong governance framework in place are all necessary steps in the process of developing a debt management strategy. Making sure debt managers are accountable for successfully carrying out the plan is another step in this procedure. It is equally important to understand that a strategy cannot be developed in a vacuum and that its viability and applicability are influenced by the macroeconomic climate and the stage of domestic market growth. The largest financial portfolio in a nation is typically one of its government's debt portfolios. It often involves complex financial structures and government disclosures that carry significant risks on the balance sheet. Governments are also more vulnerable to economic and financial shocks when their debt portfolios are large and poorly planned, which has frequently been a major contributing factor to economic crises. An increase in debt might result from higher public investment, higher government spending, lower tax revenues, or other fiscal developments. From a Keynesian viewpoint, fiscal expansion increases debt levels while also increasing GDP, particularly through the spending multiplier mechanism. This advantageous effect is likely to last, however, primarily in the short term. There is no agreement on the direction and size of this growth in debt's influence on real GDP, despite the fact that it is crucial for assessments of the sustainability of the public debt. The analysis of the public debt-economic growth nexus has received considerable attention. Theoretically, there are arguments in favor of a positive, negative, or neutral impact of government borrowing on the economy. The crowding-out effect, according to the neo-classical theory, is a negative effect of public debt. Borrowing from the government may raise interest rates, which would inhibit private investment and economic expansion. According to Ricardian equivalence, the government's debt and deficit have no bearing on economic expansion. Increased savings compensate for the increase in demand brought on by government consumption financed by debt. People begin saving more money because of getting ready for potential tax hikes that may be necessary to pay off significant amounts of public debt.

In order to increase economic activity and achieve higher economic growth, major expenditures are required in infrastructure, technical research and development, machine learning, artificial intelligence, human capital, and environmental protection. The primary sources of funding for these investments are taxes and governmental borrowing. Taxes have a limited ability to generate revenue in the Least Developed Countries (LDCs), such as Nepal, due to low levels of personal income, few economic transactions, and a possibility of an increased burden on local economic units. Because of this, public debt is seen as a viable tool to finance government spending and development initiatives. In this sense, the term "public debt" refers to the total amount of debt that the government has taken on to finance and meet its development budget. Nepal was severely affected by COVID-19 at an unfavorable period. In FY2019/20, Nepal's state debt increased by 35.5 percent because of rising costs to combat COVID-19 and declining tax receipts because of a downturn in economic activity. The government in 2018 established the national Public Debt Management Office (PDMO). Its new employees, who were transferred to PDMO from other government agencies, need instruction in crucial debt management procedures. Additionally, the knowledge required for sensible debt management techniques was dispersed among several public entities.

Literature Review

The function of public debt has historically been a topic of intense discussion among economists. Generally speaking, classical economics opposed public borrowing. They made the erroneous assumption that over time, real GDP will naturally catch up to potential GDP. Therefore, for this reason, classical economists did not favor counter-cyclical fiscal policy. They also believed that the private sector could use resources more effectively than the state sector. They supported a balanced budget. For two reasons, external debt has been the subject of previous research. First off, domestic borrowing only moves resources within the country, whereas external borrowing might increase a country's access to resources. In light of this, only external debt causes a "transfer" concern (Keynes, 1929). Second, because developing country central banks are unable to produce the hard currency required to pay off foreign debt, external borrowing is frequently linked to risks that could trigger debt crises. In this essay, I make the

case that the old division between foreign and domestic debt may not be as useful in the current context of growing financial integration and open capital accounts.

A significant portion of professionals believes in the "Barro-Ricardo statement of equivalence" in relation. The idea is that raising taxes or issuing debt, the two methods of financing the deficit, are essentially equivalent. The claim is delaying taxation by using bond issuance to finance deficits. The government will need to increase taxes in the future to pay off the debt, and (with correct discounting) there will not be any difference between current and future taxes. People become aware that they will soon have to pay more taxes when the government borrows money to cover its deficit. People, therefore, do not spend more money because of expansionary fiscal policy since they are saving it up to pay taxes in the future. Therefore, the argument implies that because of debt financing, private savings will rise (Barro, 1989). Economists often advise against borrowing from the central bank because it is thought that this kind of financing is very inflationary. Commercial banks are the primary owners of the public debt. Despite the fact that this sort of debt is thought to be less inflationary than debt owed to a central bank, there is a view that it discourages private investment. However, the portfolio-balance model of demand for money indicates that the amount of debt that people hold does put upward pressure on interest rates. This model proposes that asset owners allocate their demand for financial assets among a range of accessible assets, maximizing a risk-return trade-off. The topic of portfolio balancing involves money as a risk-free asset. People expect more money as their debt holdings grow in order to cover the possible risk associated with these debts. Due to the surplus demand for money, interest rates typically increase when the money supply is static (Dornbusch, 1975).

The external or foreign source is another significant source. Especially in developing nations, borrowing from abroad has been a prominent element (Gray and Woo, 2000). In effect, capital formation is financed through the use of foreign borrowing, which enables a country to invest and consume beyond the capacity of its present domestic output in addition to utilizing the resources of nations with large capital surpluses. Borrowing from abroad may trigger faster economic expansion. However, there is a nonlinear relationship between debt accumulation and economic development. The association is negative above a certain threshold, and it is positive up to a certain degree. The availability of resources was enhanced by foreign resource inflows, which helped South Asia's economy grow

(Siddiqui and Malik, 2002). A nation must, however, manage debt responsibly if it borrows from abroad. As is the situation with Pakistan, excessive foreign borrowing and incorrect use of that money result in onerous debt payment and a nation's mounting debt, which imposes restrictions on future economic policy and, consequently, growth (Kemal A.R. 2002).

Objective

The major objective of this article is to analyze the current status and composition of public debt management in Nepal whereas the specific objective to analyze the growing pattern of internal, external, and overall public debt; and to make a relative study of the growth of the public debt with the growth rate of real GDP and rate of inflation.

Methodology

This article is based on the thematic review of existing literature, which is collected from secondary data and information. The secondary data is taken by reviewing the related reports, policy documents, journal articles, books, and other relevant documents published in Nepali and English languages. This article has analyzed the findings of previous research work most especially in a thematic approach.

Public Debt Management in Global Economy

Global sovereign debt is expected to climb by 9.5% to a record \$71.6 trillion in 2022, while fresh borrowing is also broadly set to remain elevated (Smith, 2022). According to the Institute of International Finance (IIF), emerging market borrowing led by China will raise the global debt mountain to a record \$303 trillion in 2021, despite the fact that the global debt-to-GDP ratio has improved as established economies have recovered (Wilkes, 2022). The growth in the total amount of debt was down from the \$33 trillion increase in 2020, when COVID-19-related spending surged, to the \$10 trillion increase in 2019. However, emerging markets accounted for more than 80% of last year's increased debt burden, with total debt reaching \$100 trillion (Wilkes, 2022).

Figure 1: Total Global Debt Surpassed \$300 trillion in 2021

Source: IIF, BIS, IMF and National Sources, Haver

New sovereign borrowing is expected to reach \$10.4 trillion in 2022, almost a third above the average prior to the Covid-19 pandemic, according to the latest global borrowing report from S&P Global Ratings (Smith, 2022). According to the International Monetary Fund (IMF), the proportion of low-income nations at high risk of or already in debt distress has more than doubled since 2015, rising from 30% to 60%, with some of these countries facing an urgent need to restructure their debt (IMF 2022, Chabert et al. 2022). However, not only low-income countries are feeling the pinch. A rising number of middle-income countries are likewise burdened by significant debt servicing obligations. The United Nations Development Programme projected last year that 72 of 120 low- and middle-income countries were vulnerable to debt (Jensen 2021), and the situation has not improved since then. The two years following the beginning of the epidemic have seen a significant growth in the debt-to-GDP ratios and the external debt service as a percentage of government revenue, both of which had already been rising before the Covid-19 problem. 135 out of 148 nations examined in the Global South are thought to be critically indebted, according to the Global Sovereign Debt Monitor 2022 and erlassjahr.de (2022). Particularly critically indebted is a term used to identify 39 nations. This is a rise of more than three times from the number before the pandemic.

Public Debt Management in Nepal

As we know that Nepal is one of the world's least developed nations (LDCs). The serious lack of resources to finance public spending is one of the main issues facing all LDCs. They need to borrow money in such circumstances. Public borrowing is becoming a crucial method of government financing in the modern world, not just for LDCs but also for rich nations, alongside other revenue sources including tax and non-tax revenue. When someone's income falls short of their needs, they should borrow money from someone or somewhere. When its revenue cannot cover its spending, the government should borrow money in a similar way. The budgeting practiced by the government of Nepal is not very old. In 1951 A.D., budgeting was first used. Following that, we frequently face deficit budgeting. The government of Nepal can finance its budget deficit through three different channels: external loans, internal loans, and changes in its cash reserves. Public debt has thus been a crucial weapon in Nepal's budgetary policy. However, Nepal's governmental debt was incurred 11 years after budgetary practice began. Therefore, the history of our public debt is not very old. In contrast to 1963, when it began taking foreign loans, the government began taking domestic loans in 1962. Former USSR and UK were Nepal's first international creditors (Acharya, 1998). Following that, the public debt plays a significant role in the federal budget. Deficit financing has very momentous role in the annual budget of the government of Nepal.

According to the Public Debt Management Office (PDMO), Nepal's total debt reached NPR. 2.01 trillion, which is equivalent to 41.47 percent of Nepal's gross domestic product (GDP). The share of external debt is 21.14 percent of the GDP, according to its latest report for the fiscal year 2021-22. The share of debt to the GDP was just 25.65 percent in the fiscal year 2015-16, according to the PDMO. According to the newly enacted Public Debt Management Act, external debt is capped at one-third of the previous fiscal year's GDP. This is the first time Nepal sought to limit external debt through public debt caps. Likewise, the maximum internal loans that the government can raise with the new law is NPR. 256 billion for the current fiscal year 2022-23. Besides encouraging prudence in accepting external debt, it will also encourage the government to make timely debt payments so that it can borrow more. Although Nepal's debt position is not particularly alarming, the PDMO reports that during the fiscal year 2018-19, the

total amount owed by the country climbed from NPR. 1 trillion to NPR. 2 trillion. The percentage of external debt has now reached a level that is equivalent to 21.14 percent of GDP, but Nepal still has room to increase the acceptance of foreign debt by roughly 12 percent after the new law is put into effect. Nepal is not a country with high levels of debt because the majority of loans have protracted payback periods and moderate interest rates. At the same time as Nepal is determined to limit its foreign borrowing, a number of countries, notably the well-known Sri Lanka, are presently going through a debt crisis.

Moreover, Nepal's budget deficit, which occurs when the expenses of the government exceed its revenue, has been gradually increasing over the years. In FY 2020/21, the budget deficit as a percentage of GDP was 7.1%. Deficit financing plays an important role in the yearly budget presented by the Government of Nepal, as it consists of 29.64% of the government budget. Annually, it has been increasing by 19.86% on average. A continuous and increasing fiscal deficit in Nepal, resulting in the government continuously taking loan for deficit financing. While public debt is an important source of income for the Nepali government and is important for a developing nation like Nepal, relying heavily on borrowing can be costly and risky.

Current Trend and Public Debt Condition of Nepal

Historically, Nepal has been borrowing domestically and internationally to meet its development requirement; the Government of Nepal raised its first internal loan in 1951, and its first external debt in 1963. The external loan is the highest source of deficit financing, followed by internal debt and change in cash reserves, respectively. Due to an increase in expenditure demands of post-earthquake reconstruction and federalism, government borrowing has increased significantly in recent years. In five years to 2020/21, total public debt increased by 148%. At the end of 2021/22, the total government debt reached NPR 2,011.95 billion, out of which external debt consisted of NPR 1025.84 billion and internal debt consisted of NPR 986.10 billion whereas external debt increased by 5.47% and internal debt increased by 12.16%. The total debt-to-GDP ratio, which is a metric comparing country's public debt to its total economic output for the year, gives an overview of how capable a country is in paying its debt. It is an indicator of how much debt a country owes and how much it produces to pay off its debt. The debt-

to-GDP ratio of Nepal at the end of FY 2021/22 was 41.47%, where the external debt-to-GDP ratio was 21.14% and the internal debt-to-GDP ratio was 20.32%. This is a sharp increase as compared to the FY 2018/19, when the total public debt was estimated to be 30.1% of GDP, out of which the external debt to GDP ratio was 17% and the domestic debt to GDP ratio was 13.1%. The debt to GDP ratio has exceeded the periodic targets of the Sustainable Development Goals and the final 2030 target of 35%.

Figure 2: Outstanding Domestic Debt and Foreign Debt of the Government of Nepal

(in NPR Millions)

P = Provisional Estimated, R= Revised Estimated Source: Current Macroeconomic and Financial Situation Tables Based on Annual data of 2021/22 Nepal Rastra Bank (Aryal, 2022)

Based on the public debt trend, total debt position has seen almost 35% growth on year-to-year basis. The unprecedented health crisis due to the Covid-19 related pandemic has increased government spending substantially while revenue remained below the target which ultimately increased net borrowing requirement during the fiscal Year 2076/77. Total debt has touched 37.7% percentage of GDP at the end of Fiscal year 2076/77. The variation is mainly due to the increase in external debt reflecting: (i) the increase in disbursement of the pre-negotiated loans from multilateral creditors; (ii) entered into the moratorium of debts with

the G20 countries with the Debt Service Suspension Initiative (DSSI) and (iii) fluctuations on the foreign exchange rate.

Table 1: Annual Growth Rate of Outstanding Debt of the Government of Nepal

Year	Growth Rate
2011/12	18%
2012/13	4%
2013/14	2%
2014/15	-2%
2015/16	15%
2016/17	12%
2017/18	31%
2018/19	14%
2019/20 ^R	36%
2020/21 ^P	22%

Source: Calculated based on NRB's data on the outstanding debt of the Government of Nepal (Aryal, 2022)

Over the period of FY 2011/12 to 2020/21, the public debt of the Government of Nepal has been significantly increasing (Figure 2 and Table 1). Between FY 2011/12 and FY 2019/20, the Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of the public debt of Nepal was 7%. The reason behind the increasing public debt of Nepal is the significant increase in the size of the budget over time; the expenditure of the Government of Nepal has been increasing, and the expenditure of the government is higher than its revenue.

Table 2: Status of Current Debt of the Government of Nepal

Debt Status	Amount in Billions			Ratio with GDP		
	2019/20	2020/21	2021/22	2019/20	2020/21	2021/22
Internal Debt	813.37	934.15	1027.30	20.9	21.8	21.2
External Debt	613.21	800.32	984.28	15.8	18.7	20.3
Total Debt	1427.18	1734.47	2011.58	36.5	40.5	41.5

(Source: Calculated based on NRB Data, 2022)

According to recent data of PDMO, the total government debt reached NPR 2007.84 billion at the end of the 1st quarter of F/Y 2079/80 (Oct, 2022). Out of this amount, external debt is NPR 1050.23 billion and internal debt is NPR 957.61 billion. During this time, the total debt to GDP ratio reached 21.64 percent and for internal debt to GDP ratio reached 19.73 percent. Public debt stood at 41.5 percent of GDP at the end of FY22 and is split approximately evenly between external concessional and domestic sources. According to this trend, the fiscal deficit is projected to fall from 3.4 percent of GDP in FY23 to 2.4 percent in FY24 as remaining COVID-19 support measures and FY23 electoral spending end, and the government implements revenue-enhancing reforms. Total public debt is projected to decrease to 40.7 percent of GDP by FY24.

Nepal-Debt Management Framework (DMF) Partnership And Pandemic

Nepal was severely affected by COVID-19 at an unfavorable period. In FY2019/20, Nepal's state debt increased by 35.5 percent as a result of rising costs to combat COVID-19 and declining tax receipts because of a downturn in economic activity. The government in 2018 established the national Public Debt Management Office (PDMO). Its new employees, who were transferred to PDMO from other government agencies, need instruction in crucial debt management procedures. Additionally, the knowledge required for sensible debt management techniques was dispersed among several public entities. Nepal reacted quickly, with assistance from the Debt Management Facility (DMF). The DMF is a multi-

donor trust fund that the World Bank and the International Monetary Fund jointly manage. It provides advisory services, training, and peer-to-peer learning to over 80 developing nations worldwide in order to improve their debt management capability, processes, and institutions. Since its initial Debt Management Performance Assessment in 2011, Nepal has benefited from DMF assistance (Hona, 2021). The Nepalese government started a debt reform strategy in 2019 that was divided into four basic components: (i) evaluating the legal framework; (ii) managerial structure; (iii) recording and reporting capabilities; and (iv) domestic debt issuances. However, the pandemic's emergence altered the priorities. The Nepalese debt management (PDMO) learned about several kinds of debt instruments and their cash flows throughout the DMF course. They discovered how to access data from the system that could be immediately extracted, such as currency and interest rate information. They also acquired the knowledge necessary to determine the cost and risk indicators, which are crucial for creating a debt management strategy.

Debt Trap in Nepalese Economy

A Debt trap is a situation where you are forced to take new loans in order to repay your existing debt obligations. In addition, before you know what a debt trap is, you fall into a situation where the amount of debt you owe takes a turn for the worse and spirals out of control. Such a situation typically arises when your debt obligations exceed your repayment capacity. For instance, the income you generate is insufficient to clear your debt; the interest standing up on your outstanding loan amount will start to pile up quickly. This will eventually lead you to avail fresh new loans to clear off the piled-up interest, thereby falling into a debt trap. Many policymakers and economic experts in Nepal are complacent due to the country's debt to gross domestic product ratio, which is one of the lowest when compared to other South Asian countries. Typically, they draw a direct parallel between Nepal and Sri Lanka and assert that Nepal may not be going through a financial crisis. Additionally, managing resources for the rising debt service payments in the years to come would undoubtedly be difficult if the nation is unable to generate enough cash to cover its ongoing expenses. Because of the inefficient use of the limited resources, unnecessary and wasteful spending is also spreading like an epidemic. All of them indicate that Nepal is moving closer to a debt trap. When a nation borrows more than it can afford to pay back in interest

and spends money on unnecessary and wasteful projects, it is said to be in a debt trap. Debt-trap diplomacy is a term used to describe how the Chinese government uses the debt loads of smaller countries for geopolitical purposes, and it was developed by Brahma Chellaney, a professor of strategic studies at the Centre for Policy Research in New Delhi.

There are 21 projects in Nepal that are considered national treasures in many fields, including roads, irrigation, hydropower, an international airport, a sacred site, a railroad, drinking water, and conservation. Quite a few of these projects are being carried out with substantial loan amounts from foreign aid. All of these projects are crucial, but due to excessive cost increases brought on by ongoing deadline delays and a low rate of return, Nepal now has more debt than it did before. High debt burdens can be seen in the Sikta and Babai irrigation projects, the Pokhara Regional International Airport, and the Melamchi Drinking Water Project, among other projects. The projects of national pride might have also included higher priority, mega-scale, and complex projects, which could have had a significant positive impact on the country's economy and development with a high rate of return by allowing the government to pay off its debts on schedule. In addition to the national pride projects, several sectoral projects with loan financing are also dealing with heavy debt loads. The Public Debt Management Office of Nepal estimates that at the end of FY 2078/79, the total amount of government debt was NPR 2,011.95 billion (July 2022). Out of this sum, NPR 1025.84 billion is owed to foreign creditors, and NPR 986.10 billion is owed to domestic creditors. The entire amount of debt owed by the Nepalese government during the fiscal year 1978–1979 increased by 8.65% during that time. Both internal and external debt have grown by 12.16 percent. At the end of FY 2078/79, the total debt to GDP ratio was 41.47 percent, while the external debt to GDP ratio was 21.14 percent and the internal debt to GDP ratio was 20.32 percent.

Nepal received the most loans from the International Development Association, followed by the Asian Development Bank. Among bilateral donors, Japan is Nepal's largest creditor. The Chinese debts are essentially loans from China's Export-Import Bank for various economic projects. India is the second largest bilateral creditor after China. The country's reliance on foreign and internal loans is out of proportion to its performance and ability to repay. And relying heavily on debts may be risky for a small country like Nepal. Nepal lacks transparency in

its overall debt management, and without increased transparency, it may face significant financial concerns. In Nepal, debt transparency might be greatly improved. The public publication of lending contracts would allow lawmakers, media, and civil society organizations to evaluate them, as well as other lenders to have complete information before making additional loans. As a result, Nepal requires rigorous homework and increased openness at all phases, from project formulation to debt negotiation. Finally, Nepal must demonstrate better skill in evaluating new projects to ensure their feasibility and financial sustainability. It must strengthen its own bargaining power with development partners to ensure that people benefit from the projects and that debt is used for economic growth and improved income production in order to repay it comfortably.

Future Consequences

Increasing public debt is a peculiar problem for debt management and poses a challenge to the economy. A study on the effect of public debt on Nepal's economic growth discovered that government borrowing has mostly been funded on unproductive sectors, resulting in the government's lack of money and having to take out an additional new loan to pay off the old loans. Further, this has resulted in an increase in the total outstanding public debt and its interest but no improvement in the debt repayment potential. Moreover, while the country is borrowing more for deficit financing, a large portion of the government's budget is being used for debt principal repayment and interest payment. While the government is estimated to earn NPR 1.24 trillion in revenues in FY 2022/23, it plans to pay 15% of its estimated revenue to foreign and domestic creditors. Overall, this negatively impacts the government's ability to finance development activities within the country.

It is also important to analyze the debt situation of the country with regard to the foreign exchange reserve. A country needs to pay off its external debt with its foreign exchange reserve. While external loans are cheaper than domestic loans, external loans carry risk of foreign exchange fluctuations. The debt liability in the domestic currency terms of Nepal is on the rise due to the depreciation of the Nepali rupee against the US dollar. The outstanding debt-to-foreign exchange ratio, which was 26% in 2016/17, increased to 57% in 2020/21. The depleting foreign currency reserve, and the increasing government borrowing from external creditors, could make debt payments in foreign currency increasingly difficult.

This could push the country into the vicious cycle of borrowing more to pay off the existing external debt.

Summary and Conclusion

The public debt management office is currently making several efforts to reduce borrowing and boost the nation's foreign reserve exchange. To stop the mounting debt, the newly passed Public Debt Management Act set a limit on external debt at one-third of the GDP of the prior fiscal year. The government can also raise a maximum internal loan of NPR 256 billion under the new law for the current fiscal year 2022–2023. These measures are intended to prevent the government from borrowing carelessly and to motivate it to pay down its debts on schedule so that it can borrow more money in the future. In the Nepalese economy, public debt is climbing. Public debt is growing at an average pace of 36% in 2019/2020 and 22% in 2020/21. When discussing the breakdown of public debt, external loans account for an average share that is higher than internal loans. The share of internal loans, however, is substantially higher in the latter period than the share of external loans. The economy appears to be growing at a slow pace. One of the main issues facing the Nepalese economy is the country's slow rate of economic growth and high rate of inflation. Therefore, efforts should be made to quicken growth so that more jobs may be created and people's incomes can rise. To achieve this, strategies that raise the amount of overall supply should be used. In order to achieve this, investments should be raised and new technology adoption should be encouraged. The maintenance of price stability should get similar attention.

In addition to introducing policies to help reduce the Government of Nepal's debt, the country needs to also use the borrowed money effectively. Currently, borrowing has mostly been utilized in unproductive sectors. To be able to repay the loans in the long term, the Government of Nepal should use the borrowed money to create a sustainable economy by investing in productive sectors with high levels of efficiency. This is especially more relevant now as Nepal is preparing to graduate from the LDC group in 2026, due to which Nepal may lose its benefits of a lower rate of interest. Therefore, to avoid further increasing Nepal's debt burden after LDC graduation, the country should strategize and use the borrowed money more efficiently.

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